

hatchability 81%. Males lived 27 days and females 33 days, and fecundity was 513 eggs. Data are equivalent to BPH biotype 1 data from TN1 plants.

Leersia-reared BPH fed little on rice plants, as indicated by low amounts of excreta, and did not survive on TN1 and several resistant varieties. Rice-plant-reared BPH populations, tested in the greenhouse, did not live on *Leersia*, but could contribute to the rice-feeding BPH gene pool through intermingling.

A crossing experiment was conducted to determine if *Leersia*-reared and rice-plant-reared BPH mate and to assess the virulence of the offspring. Individual fifth-instar nymphs of *Leersia*-reared BPH were placed in test tubes containing *Leersia* cuttings and greenhouse rice-reared BPH were placed in test tubes containing TN1 seedlings. Using adults that emerged simultaneously, crosses of

Survival of progeny from crosses between *Leersia* brown planthopper (BPH) and rice-reared BPH at 15 days after being placed on *Leersia* and TN1 plants.

Leersia BPH and rice-reared BPH were caged on *Leersia* and TN1 plants planted together in a clay pot. When eggs hatched, 10 newly emerged nymphs were caged on separate potted *Leersia* and TN1 plants. Some F₁ progenies sur-

vived (see figure) and produced F₂ progenies on *Leersia* and TN1 plants. If intermingling also occurs under field conditions, the wild *Leersia* BPH population can contribute to BPH field infestation. *h*

The flea beetle as a rice pest in Assam, India

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The flea beetle *Chaetonema basalis* Baly. was studied on rice plants during transplanting and tillering stages in ahu (March-July) and sali (July-December)

1980-81 in Assam, India. Mild infestations were reported in Barpeta Agricultural Subdivision, Kamrup, Assam, but there was no significant economic damage.

Adults are small, round, black, shining beetles about 1.5 to 2 mm long. They are found on leaves and jump when disturbed. They feed by scraping the green matter from leaves, leaving short straight lines on the leaf surface

that are parallel to leaf veins. Damage resembles that caused by the rice hispa *Dicladispa armigera*. Later, ends of affected leaves turn brown and wither. Heavily infested fields look scorched. In severely infested fields 25-40 beetles/hill can be found.

A rabi oilseed survey has shown that the pest also attacks mustard pods during winter. *h*

Rice thrips in Mymensingh, Bangladesh

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Rice thrips *thrips oryzae* Williams have become a major problem at the INA experimental farm, Mymensingh, and in adjacent areas. During 1982 aus season (summer rice) all varieties on the farm (high yielding and local) were severely damaged. In some cases infestation was 100%.

Infestation occurs in seedling and early growth stages. Thrips nymphs and adults suck sap from the leaves. In heavy infestation plants may dry.

Thrips increase might have been

caused by the long winter and summer drought and by the destruction of natural enemies through heavy insecticide application. Infestation decreased with the onset of rainy season. *h*

Status of the brown planthopper in Thailand

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Brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* (Stål) is one of the most destruc-

tive rice pests in central Thailand. In 1981, 36,000 ha were severely damaged. In a survey of pest status April-June 1981, BPH populations and natural enemies were estimated by direct counting (50 hills/field) and sweep net (50 sweeps/field) at 42 sites in 9 provinces, BPH eggs and egg parasites were sampled by dissecting 10 random hills at each location. BPH was in 95% of samples. Density was 204 adults and nymphs/50 hills and 6.5/50 sweeps (see table). Rice ragged stunt disease (RSV) was in 43% of sites, averaging 5% infected hills. Natural enemies — damselflies, wolf spider *Lycosa pseudoannulata*, long-jawed orb weaver *Tetragnatha* spp, and coccinellid beetle *Micrapis discolor* — were abundant. Mirid bug *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis* population was